

Azulene as Anomaly in Triplet-State Engineering Via Bromination and/or Carbonylation: Internal Conversion Overrides Intersystem Crossing

Kavya Vinod,¹ Claire Tonnelé,^{2*} Anup Rana,³ Swathi Krishna P. E.,¹ Juan Carlos Roldao,^{2,3} Henrik Ottosson,^{3*} David Casanova,² Mahesh Hariharan^{1*}

¹School of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Thiruvananthapuram, Maruthamala P.O., Vithura, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala 695551, India.

²Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC), 20018 Donostia, Euskadi, Spain; IKERBASQUE–Basque Foundation for Science, 48009 Bilbao, Euskadi, Spain.

³Department of Chemistry–Ångström Laboratory, Uppsala University, Box 516, Uppsala 751 20, Sweden

Supporting Information (SI)

Table of Contents

Section 1: Materials and Methods	4
1.1 Femtosecond Transient Absorption (fsTA) Measurements.....	4
1.2 Global Analysis.....	4
1.3 Nanosecond Transient Absorption Measurements.....	5
1.4 Computational Details.....	5
Section 2: Synthesis	6
Section 3: Tables	8
Table S1: The crystallographic details of Az-5.....	8
Table S2: Vertical excitation energies (in eV) for the S0 → S1 and S0 → S2 transitions of Az and the substituted azulenes Az-1 to Az-5 along with their oscillator strengths obtained from the ADC(2)/def2-TZVP calculations at their respective ADC(2)/def2-TZVP optimized geometries.....	8
Table S3: Energy difference (in eV) of the molecular orbitals of substituted azulenes Az-1 to Az-5 with respect to Az	8
Table S4: Vertical excitation energies (in eV) for the four low-lying singlets of Az and the substituted azulenes Az-1 to Az-5 obtained from the ADC(2)/def2-TZVP calculations at their respective ADC(2)/def2-TZVP	9

	optimized ground state geometries.....	
Table S5:	Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganization energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for Az.....	9
Table S6:	Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganization energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for Az-3.....	9
Table S7:	Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganization energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for Az-4	9
Table S8:	Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganization energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for Az-5	10
Table S9:	Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganization energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for Az-3asym	10
Section 4: Figures		11
Figure S1:	Molecular orbitals involved in the excitations to the singlet excited states of Az, computed at the ADC(2)/def2-SVP level at the ground state geometry.....	11
Figure S2:	(a) FsTA spectra of Az ; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of Az ; c) Population kinetics of Az	11
Figure S3:	(a) FsTA spectra of Az-1 ; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of Az-1 ; c) Population kinetics of Az-1	12
Figure S4:	(a) FsTA spectra of Az-2 ; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of Az-2 ; c) Population kinetics of Az-2	12
Figure S5:	(a) NsTA spectra of Az ; b) NsTA spectra of Az-1 upon 355 nm excitation	13
Figure S6:	(a) NsTA spectra of Az-2 ; b) NsTA spectra of Az-3 upon 355 nm excitation	13
Figure S7:	(a) NsTA spectra of Az-4 ; b) NsTA spectra of Az-5 upon 355 nm excitation	13
Figure S8:	Relationship between SOC constant (in cm^{-1}) and $S_2 \rightarrow T_4$ ISC times (in s)	14

according to the Marcus model (equation S1) with energy parameters (inset) corresponding to **Az**, computed at the ADC(2)/def2-SVP level at the S_2 state geometry. Red marker indicates the minimum SOCC value to reach the ISC nanosecond regime.....

Section 5: Characterization Data	15
Figure S9: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az in CDCl_3	15
Figure S10: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az in CDCl_3	15
Figure S11: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az-1 in CDCl_3	16
Figure S12: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az-1 in CDCl_3	16
Figure S13: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az-2 in CDCl_3	17
Figure S14: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az-2 in CDCl_3	17
Figure S15: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az-3 in CDCl_3	18
Figure S16: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az-3 in CDCl_3	18
Figure S17: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az-4 in CDCl_3	19
Figure S18: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az-4 in CDCl_3	19
Figure S19: ^1H NMR spectrum of Az-5 in CDCl_3	20
Figure S20: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Az-5 in CDCl_3	20

Section 1: Materials and Methods

All chemicals were procured from commercial suppliers and utilized as received without further purification. All reactions were carried out in oven-dried glassware prior to use. Solvents were dried and distilled by standard laboratory purification techniques. TLC analyses were performed on re-coated aluminum plates of silica gel 60 F254 plates (0.25 mm, Merck), and developed TLC plates were visualized under short- and long-wavelength UV lamps. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel of 200-400 mesh employing a solvent polarity correlated with the TLC mobility observed for the substance of interest. Steady-state photophysical measurements of the derivatives were conducted in a 10 mm path length cuvette for solution-state measurements. Absorption and emission spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV-3600 UV-VIS-NIR and Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluorolog spectrometers, respectively. The UV-vis absorption spectra in the solution-state were measured using the transmittance mode. The solution-state fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ_F) was measured relatively with respect to perylene as standard.

The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Agilent MR Spectrometer and Bruker Advance DPX spectrometer respectively. The residual solvent peak in NMR used as reference. The relative concentration method used for quantitative ^1H NMR measurement. HRMS data were obtained using a Bruker MicroTOF-Q II instrument operation at ambient temperature.

1.1 Femtosecond Transient Absorption (fsTA) Measurement

A Spectra-Physics Mai Tai SP mode-locked laser, with an operating frequency of 86 MHz and emitting light at 800 nm, served as the seed for a Spectra-Physics Spitfire ace regenerative amplifier. The regenerative amplifier operated at a repetition rate of 1 kHz and produced an output energy of 5.5 mJ. A fraction of the amplified output was utilized to generate the required pump pulse through TOPAS. Simultaneously, the remaining 800 nm pulse underwent an optical delay within an ExciPro pump-probe spectrometer. A sapphire crystal introduced into this path generated a white light continuum, which was then split into two streams, serving as probe and reference pulses. Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of the sample were captured using a dual diode array detector with a detection window of 200 nm and an optical delay of 3.6 ns. To enable accurate deconvolution of the transient absorption data, an instrument response function (IRF) was determined. The IRF, established through a solvent (10% benzene in methanol) two-photon absorption, was approximately 110 fs at around 530 nm. An 80% neutral density filter regulated incident flux on the sample. For the fsTA measurements of **Az**, the excitation wavelength was 340 nm and for **Az-1** to **Az-5**, the excitation wavelength was 370 nm. The magic angle polarization $\sim 54.7^\circ$, between pump and probe pulses was used to ensure an isotropic signal of the sample.

1.2 Global Analysis

Global analyses of the fsTA and nsTA spectra were performed using the Glotaran software. The procedure evaluates the instrument time response function and the group velocity dispersion of the white continuum and allows one to compute decay time constants and dispersion-compensated spectra. In global analysis, all the wavelengths were analyzed concurrently, employing a sequential model to give evolution-associated difference spectra (EAS). The EAS indicates the evolution of the spectra in time and does not necessarily denote a real physical/chemical species. EAS designates the spectral changes that occur with their associated time constants.

1.3 Nanosecond Transient Absorption Measurements

Nanosecond laser transient absorption experiments were performed using an Applied Photophysics Model LKS-60 laser kinetic spectrometer. The nitrogen-purged sample solutions were excited with the third harmonic (355 nm, pulse duration ~8 ns) of a Quanta Ray INDI-40–10 series pulsed Nd:YAG laser.

1.2 Computational Details

All geometries were optimized using the second-order algebraic diagrammatic construction [ADC(2)] method with the def2-TZVP basis set, as implemented in TURBOMOLE. On the basis of these equilibrium structures, single point calculations were performed at the same level of theory to obtain vertical energies. Spin-orbit coupling (SOC) between the relevant singlet and triplet states was computed using TDDFT with the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDA) at the ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP level, considering a mean-field treatment of the 2-electron part of the Breit-Pauli operator as implemented in Q-Chem. Individual rates for intersystem crossing (ISC) between excited singlet and triplet states were evaluated using Fermi's golden rule within the Marcus approximation:

$$k_{ISC} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \frac{V_{SOC}^2}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda k_B T}} \exp\left[-\frac{(\lambda - \Delta E)^2}{4\lambda k_B T}\right] \quad (S1)$$

with k_B the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, λ the reorganization energy, ΔE and V_{SOC} the adiabatic gap and SOC between the initial singlet and final triplet state, respectively. Here, λ is evaluated as the average of the energy variation in the final triplet state when switching from the singlet equilibrium geometry to the triplet equilibrium geometry and the energy variation in the initial singlet state when switching from the triplet equilibrium geometry to the singlet equilibrium geometry.

Alternatively, $S_2 \rightarrow T_4$ ISC rates were computed using effective time-dependent (TD) approaches considering the Franck-Condon approximation and with Herzberg-Teller corrections. These calculations were performed using the ESD module implemented in ORCA, including Duchinsky rotation at 300 K and using the Adiabatic Hessian approximation, which considers the normal modes and equilibrium geometry of each states at their respective optimized geometry. S_2 and T_4 geometries were optimized at the ω B97X-D/def2-TZVP level within TDADFT using Gaussian software package. Adiabatic energy gaps were obtained from ADC(2) calculations.

Section 2: Synthesis

2.1 Synthesis of 2-bromoazulene-1,3-dialdehyde (Az-2)

A solution of 2-bromoazulene (100 mg, 0.48 mmol) in dimethylformamide (DMF) (5 mL) was placed at room temperature under argon atmosphere. Then phosphorus oxychloride (0.27 mL, 2.88 mmol) was added dropwise to the stirred mixture and the reaction mixture was heated on an oil bath at 90 °C for 5 h. The solution was cooled to the room temperature and reaction mixture was quenched by using aqueous sodium acetate solution (7.09 g, 86.4 mmol). The reaction mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (DCM) (~10 mL x 3), combined extracted DCM layer was washed three times with water (~20 mL x 3) and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The solution was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography by using DCM/pentane (1:9) as eluent to obtain pure Az-2 (67 mg, 53%) as orange red crystalline solid.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 10.51 (s, 2H), 9.93-9.96 (m, 2H), 8.10-8.15 (m, 1H), 7.97-8.10 (m, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 186.05, 150.99, 142.88, 142.47, 139.77, 135.49; HRMS (APCI): m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{BrO}_2$ (M+H): 262.9702; found: 262.9701.

2.2 Synthesis of 1,3,6-tribromoazulene (Az-4)

A solution of 6-bromoazulene (50 mg, 0.24 mmol) in DCM (5 mL) was placed at 0 °C under argon atmosphere. Then N-bromosuccinimide (86 mg, 0.48 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at 0 °C. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was quenched by using aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted by using DCM (5 mL x 3). The combined DCM layer was passed through anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography by using pentane as eluent to obtain desired product **Az-4** (81 mg, 93%) as green crystalline solid.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 7.98 (d, $J = 10.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.81 (s, 1H), 7.56 (d, $J = 10.8$ Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 138.72, 138.09, 134.73, 134.58, 127.52, 105.21; HRMS (APCI): m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{Br}_3$ (M+H): 362.8014; found: 362.8013.

2.3 Synthesis of 1,2,3-tribromoazulene (**Az-5**)

A solution of 2-bromoazulene (50 mg, 0.24 mmol) in DCM (5 mL) was placed at 0 °C under argon atmosphere. Then N-bromosuccinimide (86 mg, 0.48 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at 0 °C. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was quenched by using aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted by using DCM (5 mL x 3). The combined DCM layer was passed through anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The DCM was evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography by using pentane as eluent to obtain desired product **Az-5** (84 mg, 96%) as green crystalline solid.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 8.34 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.73 (t, $J = 10.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.36 (t, $J = 10.0$ Hz, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3), δ (ppm): 139.50, 136.25, 135.51, 130.86, 125.49, 104.61; HRMS (ESI+): m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{Br}_3$ ($\text{M}+\text{H}$): 362.8014; found: 362.8013.

Section 3: Tables

Table S1: The crystallographic details of Az-5.

Parameters	Az-5
a, b, c (Å)	a=4.120(2); b=15.807(3); c=16.475(3)
α, β, γ (°)	$\alpha=90; \beta=91.42(3); \gamma=90$
Space group	P 21/c
Formula	C ₁₀ H ₅ Br ₃
Formula weight	364.87
Volume (Å ³)	1072.5(6)
Temperature (K)	296
d_{calcd} , mg/m ³	2.260
Independent reflections	1879
R(reflections)	0.0396(1255)
wR ₂ (reflections)	0.0923(1878)
Data completeness	0.999
CCDC number	2524800

Table S2: Vertical excitation energies (in eV) for the S₀ → S₁ and S₀ → S₂ transitions of **Az** and the substituted azulenes **Az-1** to **Az-5** along with their oscillator strengths obtained from the ADC(2)/def2-TZVP calculations at their respective ADC(2)/def2-TZVP optimized geometries.

	S ₀ → S ₁			S ₀ → S ₂		
	E _v (eV)	f	E ⁰⁻⁰	E _v (eV)	f	E ⁰⁻⁰
Az	2.261 (2.24)	0.009 (0.009)	1.84 (1.81) [1.77]	3.861 (3.85)	0.005 (0.005)	3.65 (3.66) [3.50]
Az-1	2.491	0.006		3.460	0.236	
Az-2	2.505	0.006		3.362	0.000	
Az-3	2.014 (1.97)	0.010 (0.010)	1.59 (1.57) [1.62]	3.620 (3.60)	0.080 (0.074)	3.40 (3.40) [3.34]
Az-4	1.980	0.009	1.54	3.519	0.026	3.32
Az-5	2.075	0.010	1.65	3.522	0.001	3.30

*in orange: data from Veys, Escudero, J. Phys. Chem. A 2020, 124, 7228–7237 (ADC(2) energies at PBE0/6-31G(d) geometries)

*in green: E₀₋₀ experimental values

Table S3: Energy difference (in eV) of the molecular orbitals of substituted azulenes **Az-1** to **Az-5** with respect to **Az**.

	Az-1	Az-2	Az-3	Az-4	Az-5
LUMO+1	-1.15	-1.46	-0.59	-0.88	-0.75
LUMO	-0.53	-0.99	-0.53	-0.82	-0.69
HOMO	-0.89	-1.31	-0.25	-0.49	-0.46
HOMO-1	-0.70	-0.77	-0.59	-0.65	-0.42
HOMO/LUMO gap	0.37	0.32	-0.28	-0.32	-0.24

Table S4: Vertical excitation energies (in eV) for the four low-lying singlets of **Az** and the substituted azulenes **Az-1** to **Az-5** obtained from the ADC(2)/def2-TZVP calculations at their respective ADC(2)/def2-TZVP optimized ground state geometries*.

	Az	Az-1	Az-2	Az-3	Az-4	Az-5
S ₁	2.261	2.491	2.505	2.014	1.980	2.075
S ₂	3.861	3.460	3.362	3.620	3.519	3.522
S ₃	4.667	3.603	3.389	4.405	/	4.127
S ₄	4.788	4.287	3.486	4.547	/	4.308

*S₂/S₃ near-degeneracy can be lifted or reached depending on the geometry considered (S₀, S₁, or S₂)

Table S5: Adiabatic S_{1/2}-T_n energy differences (in eV), reorganisation energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s⁻¹) for **Az**.

	$\Delta E_{adiab}(T_n-S_n)$	λ	SOC (at S _n geom.)	k_{ISC}
S ₁ -T ₁	0.033	0.002	0.00	9.16E-04
S₁-T₂	0.597	0.461	0.04	4.92E+05
S ₁ -T ₃	1.115	0.209	0.09	9.95E-11
S ₁ -T ₄	2.383	0.511	0.00	1.07E-29
S ₁ -T ₅	2.980	0.269	0.00	1.15E-115
S ₂ -T ₁	-1.865	0.140	0.04	4.94E-116
S ₂ -T ₂	-1.300	0.170	0.00	1.21E-54
S ₂ -T ₃	-0.783	0.012	0.00	6.31E-217
S₂-T₄	0.486	0.130	0.04	7.71E+01
S ₂ -T ₅	1.082	0.035	0.01	1.48E-126

Table S6: Adiabatic S_{1/2}-T_n energy differences (in eV), reorganisation energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s⁻¹) for **Az-3**.

	$\Delta E_{adiab}(T_n-S_n)$	λ	SOC (at S _n geom.)	k_{ISC}
S ₁ -T ₁	0.037	0.001	0.00	8.58E-06
S₁-T₂	0.668	0.479	0.16	4.55E+06
S ₁ -T ₃	1.297	0.241	0.04	2.46E-14
S ₁ -T ₄	2.634	0.438	0.00	5.07E-45
S ₁ -T ₅	3.060	0.322	0.00	1.32E-97
S ₂ -T ₁	-1.837	0.184	0.16	2.18E-87
S ₂ -T ₂	-1.205	0.090	0.00	7.15E-78
S ₂ -T ₃	-0.576	0.196	0.00	2.26E-12
S₂-T₄	0.760	0.157	0.20	3.97E-03
S ₂ -T ₅	1.186	0.084	0.02	2.80E-56

Table S7: Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganisation energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for **Az-4**.

	$\Delta E_{adiab}(T_n-S_n)$	λ	SOC (at S_n geom.)	k_{ISC}
S_1-T_1	0.040	0.001	0.00	7.58E-06
S_1-T_2	0.685	0.474	0.33	1.66E+07
S_1-T_3	1.224	0.233	0.02	5.03E-13
S_1-T_4	2.493	0.585	0.00	1.60E-24
S_1-T_5	3.072	0.212	0.05	8.73E-158
S_2-T_1	-1.807	0.168	0.36	3.22E-91
S_2-T_2	-1.163	0.113	0.00	7.66E-61
S_2-T_3	-0.624	0.097	0.00	8.34E-23
S_2-T_4	0.645	0.169	0.31	1.41E+02
S_2-T_5	1.224	0.064	0.07	1.88E-82

Table S8: Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganisation energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for **Az-5**.

	$\Delta E_{adiab}(T_n-S_n)$	λ	SOC (at S_n geom.)	k_{ISC}
S_1-T_1	0.040	0.001	0.000	1.19E-05
S_1-T_2	0.632	0.453	0.207	8.21E+06
S_1-T_3	1.135	0.213	0.002	2.64E-14
S_1-T_4	2.321	0.543	0.000	1.81E-23
S_1-T_5	2.919	0.262	0.000	1.63E-113
S_2-T_1	-1.692	0.136	0.192	1.94E-97
S_2-T_2	-1.100	0.168	0.000	4.74E-40
S_2-T_3	-0.597	0.020	0.001	1.70E-76
S_2-T_4	0.589	0.156	0.192	2.00E+02
S_2-T_5	1.188	0.067	0.046	2.96E-73

Table S9: Adiabatic $S_{1/2}-T_n$ energy differences (in eV), reorganisation energy λ associated with the ISC process (in eV), SOC constants (Q-Chem mean-field) and associated intersystem crossing rate k_{ISC} (in s^{-1}) for **Az-3asym**.

	$\Delta E_{adiab}(T_n-S_n)$	λ	SOC (at S_n geom.)	k_{ISC}
S_1-T_1	0.024	0.020	0.01	1.94E+05
S_1-T_2	0.601	0.442	0.18	7.45E+06
S_1-T_3	1.062	0.212	0.06	8.83E-09
S_1-T_4	2.205	0.559	0.01	6.58E-17
S_1-T_5	2.852	0.254	0.03	1.55E-107
S_2-T_1	-1.660	0.162	0.17	2.86E-80
S_2-T_2	-1.083	0.169	0.02	1.11E-34
S_2-T_3	-0.623	0.083	0.02	1.10E-20
S_2-T_4	0.521	0.186	0.16	4.46E+04
S_2-T_5	1.168	0.086	0.04	1.92E-52

Table S10: Computed photoexcited properties of Az and the substituted azulenes, Az-1 to Az-5. Calculated singlet-triplet adiabatic energy gaps (ΔE_{adiab} in eV) and reorganization energies (λ in eV) were obtained at the ADC(2)/def2-TZVP level, SOCs (in cm^{-1}) values at the ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP level, and ISC rates (k_{ISC} in s^{-1}) and lifetimes (τ_{ISC} in s) were evaluated using the Marcus formalism.

Molecule	States	ΔE_{adiab} (T_n-S_n)	λ	SOC (at S_n geom.)	k_{ISC}	τ_{ISC}
Az	S ₁ -T ₂	0.597	0.461	0.04	4.92E+5	2.03E-6
	S ₂ -T ₄	0.486	0.130	0.04	7.71E+1	1.30E-2
Az-3	S ₁ -T ₂	0.668	0.479	0.16	4.55E+6	2.20E-7
	S ₂ -T ₄	0.760	0.157	0.20	3.97E-3	2.52E+2
Az-4	S ₁ -T ₂	0.685	0.474	0.33	1.66E+7	6.02E-8
	S ₂ -T ₄	0.645	0.169	0.31	1.41E+2	7.09E-3
Az-5	S ₁ -T ₂	0.632	0.453	0.21	8.21E+6	1.22E-7
	S ₂ -T ₄	0.589	0.156	0.19	2.00E+2	5.00E-3

Section 4: Figures

Figure S1: Molecular orbitals involved in the excitations to the singlet excited states of **Az**, computed at the ADC(2)/def2-SVP level at the ground state geometry.

Figure S2: (a) FsTA spectra of **Az** in toluene; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of **Az** in toluene; c) Population kinetics of **Az** in toluene.

Figure S3: (a) FsTA spectra of **Az-1** in toluene; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of **Az-1** in toluene; c) Population kinetics of **Az-1** in toluene.

Figure S4: (a) FsTA spectra of **Az-2** in toluene; b) Deconvoluted evolution-associated spectra of **Az-2** in toluene; c) Population kinetics of **Az-2** in toluene.

Figure S5: (a) NsTA spectra of **Az** in toluene; b) NsTA spectra of **Az-1** upon 355 nm excitation in toluene.

Figure S6: (a) NsTA spectra of **Az-2** in toluene; b) NsTA spectra of **Az-3** upon 355 nm excitation in toluene.

Figure S7: (a) NsTA spectra of **Az-4** in toluene; b) NsTA spectra of **Az-5** upon 355 nm excitation in toluene.

Figure S8: Relationship between SOC constant (in cm^{-1}) and $S_2 \rightarrow T_4$ ISC times (in s) according to the Marcus model (equation S1) with energy parameters (inset) corresponding to **Az**, computed at the ADC(2)/def2-SVP level at the S_2 state geometry. Red marker indicates the minimum SOCC value to reach the ISC nanosecond regime.

Section 5: Characterization Data

Figure S9: ^1H NMR spectrum of **Az** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S10: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **Az** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S11: ^1H NMR spectrum of **Az-1** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S12: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **Az-1** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S13: ^1H NMR spectrum of **Az-2** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S14: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **Az-2** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S15: ^1H NMR spectrum of **Az-3** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S16: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **Az-3** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S17: ^1H NMR spectrum of **Az-4** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S18: ¹³C NMR spectrum of **Az-4** in CDCl₃.

Figure S19: ¹H NMR spectrum of **Az-5** in CDCl₃.

Figure S20: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **Az-5** in CDCl_3 .